

Studies on Mild Steel|Molasses|Graphite Electrochemical Cell

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An electrochemical cell of the configuration : mild steel|molasses|graphite, gives an E.M.F. of 0.48 V at room temperature. Addition of Indion-225 cation exchange resin increases the E.M.F. significantly. Dilution and temperature have pronounced effect on current obtained from the cell. Though large polarization effect is observed at initial stages, the stabilized current remains constant for hours.

Molasses, a valuable byproduct of sugar industry, is a mixture of sucrose, water, fructose, glucose and other chemicals. According to the reports¹, molasses seems to be a case of mixed (ionic-electronic) conductor. However, moist state electrochemistry of molasses may be expected to open new potentialities in electrochemistry. Here, the possibility of using moist molasses in as electrochemical power source has been studied.

Results and Discussion

The E.M.F. of the title cell was initially found to be 0.488 V at 25°. The change of E.M.F. with time (Fig. 1) showed the influence of the addition of a cation exchange resin (Indion-225) on the E.M.F. of the cell. The initial and the stabilized values of E.M.F. in presence of resin were greater than that without resin. The E.M.F. was found to increase

Fig. 1. Variation of EMF with time at room temperature : (a) without any addition and (b) with 0.08 g of Indion 225 per g of molasses.

TABLE I—DATA SHOWING THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND DILUTION ON THE VARIATION OF SHORT CIRCUIT CURRENT WITH TIME AT 50°

Time min	Current (mA)*			
	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)
0	8.52	12.0	14.0	17.0
1	7.61	10.0	12.76	15.0
2	7.20	9.28	12.14	14.23
3	6.83	9.0	12.00	14.63
4	6.61	8.98	12.00	13.0
5	6.60	8.96	11.98	12.97
10	5.14	6.96	9.66	9.89
20	5.00	6.77	8.94	10.63
30	4.92	6.52	8.49	10.06
40	4.84	6.18	8.04	9.32
50	4.76	5.83	7.53	8.63
60	4.52	5.51	7.04	8.00
70	4.34	5.19	6.23	7.26
80	4.19	4.70	6.09	7.06
90	3.90	4.53	5.54	6.79
100	3.70	4.52	5.26	6.71
120	3.80	4.26	4.99	6.49
140	3.56	4.12	4.98	6.32
160	3.51	4.01	4.98	6.19
180	3.50	4.09	4.99	6.18
200	3.50	4.07	4.98	6.13
220	3.50	4.07	4.98	6.10
240	3.50	4.07	4.98	6.00

*Samples : (A) 100%, (B) 50%, (C) 33% and (D) 25% molasses.

by 0.023 V initially and by 0.04 V after stabilization when resin was added to the cell.

At room temperature (25°), the cell gave 4.18 mA of short circuit current initially. However, large polarization effect was noticed and the current rapidly decreased to a

stabilized value of 0.5 mA. At 50°, the initial current was found to be 8.5 mA and the stabilized current 3.8 mA. Dilution of molasses was found to have a pronounced effect on current. The increase in the initial and the stabilized current values due to dilution of the electrolyte are given in Table 1.

The results show that the title cell can deliver current for hours at a stretch, which suggests its application as an electrochemical power source.

Experimental

An electrochemical cell of configuration : mild steel|molasses|graphites, was fabricated by placing a rectangular mild steel electrode ($8 \times 3 \times 0.4$ cm) and a cylindrical graphite electrode (8 cm \times diameter 1.6 cm) 1.8 cm apart in 100 ml of molasses. The discharge behavior of the cell

was followed by measuring the E.M.F. and the short circuit current as a function of time at room temperature and at 50° employing a Philips 3100 multimeter.

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Reference

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